

Title	D2.1 Gap Analysis Between Ireland’s PID Strategy and the EOSC PID Policy
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Executive Summary

Ireland’s National Persistent Identifier (PID) Strategy and Roadmap and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) PID Policy are strongly aligned in principle and intent. They share a commitment to globally unique, persistent and resolvable identifiers that enable interoperability and openness. Both frameworks stress sustainability and governance and promote coordinated local and international adoption. Ireland’s roadmap translates these principles into actionable national steps, such as convening a national governing group, developing a PID concordat, establishing a central support service and identifying priority integrations. The EOSC Policy defines a set of expectations about the PIDs that will be used within the context of EOSC, supporting the vision of a European web of FAIR data and services. An assessment of the Irish Strategy with regard to EOSC PID Policy readiness offers a pragmatic pathway to implementing EOSC aligned PID infrastructure across Irish institutions.

This report examines where the Irish Strategy is already well aligned with European expectations and where additional steps will help ensure full compatibility with the EOSC. The analysis finds strong agreement on key principles and priorities, while identifying areas that should be further developed during the implementation of the Irish Strategy such as adopting EOSC PID actor profiles, developing EOSC-specific technical guidance for consistent implementation and stronger links to EOSC governance and review cycles. Addressing these gaps will help ensure that Ireland is fully prepared to connect its national research systems with European-wide infrastructures and benefit from more efficient research information workflows.

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1. Introduction

The purpose of this report is to analyse the gaps between Ireland’s existing national PID strategy¹ (hereafter ‘the Strategy’) and the EOSC PID Policy² (hereafter ‘the Policy’) to identify areas requiring action to ensure full alignment of the Strategy with EOSC frameworks. Following a summary of the key documents and context, the report presents the gap analysis and recommendations to ensure alignment with EOSC frameworks during the implementation phase of the Strategy. This analysis was funded in May 2025 under the RDA TIGER Cascade Grant Scheme, awarded jointly to Ireland’s National Open Research Forum (NORF) and HEAnet, Ireland’s National Research and Education Network and EOSC Mandated Organisation. The findings will inform the development D4.2 an EOSC Compatible National PID Recommendation for Ireland.

¹ Brown, J et al. (2024). Interoperability, openness, and impact: Recommendations and roadmap for an Irish PID Strategy. <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.sn00qt29n>

² European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (2020) A Persistent Identifier (PID) policy for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/926037>

2. Methodology

A structured analytical framework was applied using the section headings of the Policy as a baseline, i.e. principles, PID definitions, roles and responsibilities, PID applications, PID types etc. Legal and ethical considerations, although not a standalone section in the Policy, emerged as a recurring theme throughout. To reflect this, an additional category ('Legal and Ethical Considerations') was added to the analysis table. Each component of the Strategy was reviewed against these criteria to assess the level of alignment, identify gaps and to determine areas where further national development would support EOSC interoperability. The gap analysis documentation evolved during the project and was influenced by stakeholder consultation.

3. Context

3.1 A Persistent Identifier Strategy and Roadmap for Ireland

In September 2023 Ireland's National Open Research Forum (NORF) engaged MoreBrains Cooperative to undertake a review and analysis of the PID landscape in Ireland with the aim of developing an Irish PID Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) and a National PID Strategy and Roadmap with the support of the NORF PID Task Force. The project to deliver this strategy was initiated in response to Ireland's *National Action Plan for Open Research 2022-2030*³ which outlines objectives and actions for the next chapter in Ireland's transition to open research. Implementation of the *National Action Plan for Open Research* is being overseen by NORF and delivered under *Impact 2030: Ireland's Research and Innovation Strategy*.⁴

The Strategy was developed through a comprehensive, evidence-based consultation process involving multiple stakeholder groups. The approach included a national survey to assess current PID awareness and usage, a cost-benefit analysis examining potential time and money savings from PID adoption,⁵ focused discussions with three key groups (infrastructures, funding/government organisations, and research institutions), international knowledge exchange and a strategic SWOT analysis to identify strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats. These findings were then validated and refined through both online and in-person community workshops with a PID Task Force, ensuring all recommendations reflected the collective input and needs of Ireland's research community.

Key Features

The resulting strategy proposes a phased implementation roadmap out to 2030. Key to the success of the Strategy is the establishment of a national centralised PID support service. Through the provision of technical guidance, metadata standardisation, interoperability support and governance coordination the central PID support service will act as a key enabler of Ireland's

³ National Open Research Forum. (2022). National Action Plan for Open Research. <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.ff36jz222>

⁴ Government of Ireland - Rialtas na hÉireann. (2022) Impact 2030: Ireland's Research and Innovation Strategy. Publications Office of the European Union. <https://assets.gov.ie/static/documents/impact-2030-irelands-research-and-innovation-strategy.pdf>

⁵ Jones, P et al. (2024). A cost-benefit analysis for a central service to support persistent identifier implementation in Ireland. <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.nz80kt123>

integration into the EOSC and global research infrastructures. Other key features of the Strategy include:

1. **National governance model:** Establishes a cross-sector Governing Group with clearly defined roles and responsibilities for leading and sustaining PID implementation.
2. **Irish PID Concordat:** Introduces a concordat that articulates the purpose and vision of the PID strategy including specific commitments for minimum levels of PID integrations adoption, with tiers and follow-up steps to maintain progress and focus.
3. **Prioritised PID set:** Recommends consistent national use of digital object identifiers (DOIs) for outputs and for grants; Open Researcher and Contributor Identifiers (ORCID) for researchers; Research Activity Identifiers (RAIDs) for projects; and Research Organization Registry (ROR) identifiers for organisations.
4. **Shared resource library:** Provides centralised guidance, case studies, communications materials and practical tools to support consistent national messaging and uptake. Co-ordinated by the PID support service.
5. **Monitoring and evaluation:** Commits to annual progress reviews, adoption indicators, and continuous improvement based on sector needs and evolving practices.

3.2 A Persistent Identifier Policy for the European Open Science Cloud

The EOSC PID Policy was developed collaboratively by the EOSC FAIR Working Group and EOSC Architecture Working Group in 2020, targeting senior decision-makers and service providers to harmonise PID implementation across EOSC infrastructure. The Policy establishes a comprehensive framework by defining the roles and components of PID infrastructure alongside specific definitions, guidelines and usage requirements. The Policy sets forth ten guiding principles designed to ensure a viable, trusted long-term PID infrastructure for the EOSC. The Policy emphasises adherence to FAIR principles — particularly interoperability — while promoting a mature and sustainable infrastructure through regular updates that reflect evolving developments in the PID landscape. It defines the PID Ecosystem as the integrated collection of standards, services, actors and roles necessary to maintain unique and persistently resolvable identifiers. The Policy specifies six key roles (PID Authority, PID Service Provider, PID Manager, PID Owner, PID User) and two PID components (PID Scheme and PID Service). The Policy aims to foster harmonisation across PID providers and the services they offer in diverse political, regional and research contexts, offering insight into strategies to optimise PID implementations in local contexts.

3.3 EOSC Ireland

Nominated by DFHERIS as Ireland's EOSC Association Mandated Organisation, HEAnet published "Implementing the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) in Ireland"⁶ in July 2025 following extensive community engagement. This position paper proposes the establishment of an EOSC Ireland national node. EOSC Ireland will be a digital platform that connects researchers and research infrastructures across Ireland to the European-wide EOSC Federation, a stated EU priority action to accelerate open research across Europe.

The implementation of the national PID Strategy and the establishment of the centralised PID support service are recognised as foundational infrastructure for Ireland's participation in the EOSC Federation. This recognition underscores the critical interdependence between PID infrastructure and EOSC participation — without robust, interoperable PID systems, Ireland cannot effectively contribute to or benefit from the federated European research ecosystem.

⁶ Sabatino, R et al. (2025). Implementing the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) in Ireland - version 2 July 2025. Royal College of Surgeons in Ireland. Report. <https://doi.org/10.25419/rcsi.29627315.v1>

4. Gap Analysis

The Policy	Key EOSC Requirements / Focus	The Strategy Elements	Alignment Status	Notes
1. Principles	User-focused, global use, FAIR principles, independence, interoperability, trusted and sustainable infrastructure, adaptable, transparent and accountable governance. Facilitates human as well as machine interoperability.	Emphasises stakeholder engagement and participation, supports globally recognised PIDs, proposes governing group for long-term strategy delivery and a central PID service to support national infrastructure, incorporates annual review and a phased roadmap.	Mostly Aligned	The Strategy stresses the role of interoperability but could tie this more explicitly to the FAIR principles. National governance should ensure periodic reviews are aligned to EOSC timelines to facilitate integration. There is a focus in the Policy on responsiveness to user choice which could lead to more opportunity for flexibility and inclusion.
2. Generic PID Definitions	Global uniqueness, persistence, resolvability. Clarification of PID components, kernel information and need for minimal metadata profiles registered in open registries.	Explicit commitment to globally unique, resolvable PIDs; focus on interoperability and persistence across systems. Emphasis on metadata reuse and integration; recommends identifying “key integrations” and establishing technical support services.	Partial Alignment / Gap	The central support service should provide guidance to Irish institutions on the metadata structures and interfaces that make PIDs actionable by machines across systems. The management of PID services should be evaluated for FAIR compliance as well as the PIDs themselves.
3. Roles and Responsibilities	Defines the roles of the PID Scheme, PID Authority, PID Service Provider, PID Service,	Establishes a national governance group and proposes a PID Concordat outlining roles and	Mostly Aligned	The Strategy could leverage the specific roles defined in the Policy (PID Manager, PID Owner, PID

	PID Manager, PID Owner and PID User; calls for clarity of responsibilities and accountability.	responsibilities across stakeholders.		User) when developing the PID Concordat to ensure consistency with EOSC terminology and expectations.
4. PID Applications	Addresses wide variety of scientific applications, requires common API for all PID Service providers, needs to support secure mechanisms for confidential data, clear PID ownership, versioning, appropriate granularity levels, and prohibition of PID reassignment with tombstone requirements for deleted entities.	Focuses on practical adoption across Irish research lifecycle with emphasis on DOIs for outputs and grants, ORCIDs for researchers, ROR for institutions and RAIDs for projects. Prioritises cross-system integration and metadata reuse to reduce manual data entry and improve reporting.	Partial alignment	The central support service should develop guidance for Irish institutions on specific technical implementation details, drawing on the Policy and international best practice. The Strategy does not directly address the issue of granularity or the potential for growth in the PID landscape.
5. PID Types	PIDs can identify born digital entities, physical entities or conceptual entities. Physical and conceptual entities must have digital representations as FAIR Digital Objects. Different entity classes may require different attribute sets.	Identifies priority PIDs: DOIs for research outputs and grants, ORCIDs for researchers, ROR for organisations and funders, RAIDs for projects. Emphasises these PIDs' openness, free core services, and openly licensed metadata for unrestricted reuse.	Mostly Aligned	Strategy covers major entity types through specific PID endorsements. The national approach could be strengthened with explicit guidance on documenting new and emerging PIDs.
6. PID Services and Service Providers (PSP)	Specifies expectations for PSPs— basic services should have no cost to end users, consistently ready availability, sustainability plans,	Proposes a central PID support service and technical integrations; endorsement of DOIs, ORCID, ROR, RAID; emphasise priority PIDs' openness, free core services, and	Partial Alignment	The Strategy outlines the involvement of national PID consortia and places special emphasis on PIDs that sit outside the consortium model. The Policy

certification, open APIs, kernel information exposure and interoperability across PID systems. A high Technology Readiness Level is recommended (8) unless the service represents an added value PID.

openly licensed metadata for unrestricted reuse.

suggests additional support for PIDs that operate as add-ons or nice-to-haves that would facilitate greater End User choice.

7. Governance and Sustainability	Establishes principles for community governance of PID Services and PSPs, responsive to the needs of research, open research and EOSC, oversight, justifiable costs, exit plans for PSPs.	Recommends a governing group, national coordination and long-term evaluation (to 2030). The Strategy is supported by a cost-benefit analysis clearly demonstrating the cost and efficiency gain of investing in a central support service.	Partial Alignment / Gap	The central support service should incorporate the Policy’s governance principles into its standard operating procedures as appropriate.
8. Legal and Ethical Considerations (GDPR) – not a heading in the Policy	Addresses GDPR implications of PIDs, especially for personal identifiers; stresses lawful processing and response to erasure requests.	Mentions openness, equity, and inclusivity but does not extend to operational GDPR procedures related to PIDs and metadata.	Gap	The central support service should develop GDPR compliance recommendations for Irish institutions.

5. Detailed Gaps and Recommendations

5.1 Principles

The Policy sets out ten principles for establishing a viable, trusted PID infrastructure suitable for the long-term sustainability of the EOSC including policy governance, review processes and minimum review cycles. The national approach described in the Strategy strongly aligns with the principles set forth in the Policy. Whilst the Strategy does not explicitly reference the FAIR principles, the cost-benefit analysis supporting the Strategy stresses that national PID adoption will contribute to making Irish research data more FAIR.

Recommendations:

- The proposed governing group should:
 - Embed the FAIR principles explicitly in the Irish PID Concordat and expanded vision for PIDs in Ireland.
 - Include an ex officio representative of the EOSC Ireland Node on the governing group to ensure policy alignment with national EOSC activities.
 - Include an ex officio representative of HEAnet, the EOSC Association mandated organisation for Ireland, on the governing group to ensure policy alignment with the wider EOSC Federation.
 - Ensure the Irish PID Community of Practice facilitates the exchange of information on End User expectations and emerging PIDs in disciplinary or specific research contexts.

5.2 Generic PID Definitions

The Policy describes the three primary features for PIDs, underpinned by the goal of supporting and enabling FAIR research. EOSC's PID Policy requires each PID type to expose Kernel Information, a minimal, standardised metadata set that ensures identifiers are machine-readable and interoperable, with Kernel Information Profiles (KIPs) registered in open registries.

The Strategy aligns with the EOSC principles of global uniqueness, persistence, and resolvability but gives less emphasis to enabling FAIR research (see **6.1 Principles**). Actionable next steps include providing guidance on the metadata structures and interfaces that make PIDs actionable by machines across systems.

Recommendations:

- The central support service should:
 - Develop practical guidance to help repositories and systems make their PID metadata openly available through standard APIs or recognised metadata schemas, in line with EOSC's requirements for persistence.
 - Promote the adoption of priority PID schemas supported by standardised, machine-actionable metadata mappings to enable consistent interoperability.
 - Provide practical templates and mappings between local repository metadata fields and KIP elements to support implementation across HEIs and research infrastructures.

5.3 Roles and Responsibilities

The Strategy establishes a governing group and Concordat but does not adopt the Policy's role taxonomy.

Recommendations:

- The governing group should incorporate the EOSC-defined roles into the national PID Concordat and map Irish stakeholders to these roles.

5.4 PID Applications

The Policy sets expectations for how PIDs should be used across the research lifecycle, including clear rules for versioning, granularity, deletion (tombstones) and support for confidential or access-controlled data. Developing shared national guidance will help ensure that Irish PID infrastructures follow consistent, EOSC-aligned practices.

Recommendations:

- The central support service should:
 - Provide recommendations on when to issue new PIDs, how to represent versions and how to handle different levels of granularity.
 - Offer standard procedures for how systems should respond when an item is withdrawn or removed, ensuring that PIDs remain resolvable and compliant with EOSC expectations.
 - Produce implementation checklists for HEIs, researchers and repositories to support consistent national practice.

5.5 PID Types

The Strategy prioritises DOIs, ORCID, ROR and RAiD, which covers the main digital entities in current use. The Policy anticipates identifiers for physical samples, instruments, and conceptual entities such as vocabularies or workflows. The national approach will require mechanisms to assess, prioritise and integrate additional PID types.

Recommendations:

- The central support service should:
 - Conduct regular monitoring of emerging PIDs and provide recommendations to the governing group.
 - When a new PID type becomes relevant, publish short guidance documents explaining the benefits, common workflows and practical integration options for Irish institutions.
 - Pilot how emerging PIDs can be introduced, focusing on metadata, workflows and interoperability.

5.6 PID Services and Service Providers

The EOSC PID Policy outlines expectations for PID Service Providers (PSPs), including sustainability, open APIs, interoperability, and operational maturity. A coordinated national approach for selecting or assessing PID services will help ensure services used by Irish institutions meet EOSC-ready standards.

Recommendations:

- The central support service should:
 - Provide criteria and guidance to help institutions evaluate PID services aligned with EOSC expectations.
 - Produce step-by-step guidance and examples for integrating priority PIDs into common systems improving efficiency and consistency across institutions.
 - Act as a central point of contact for international providers (particularly those that fall outside the consortium model) and coordinate Ireland's participation in and community consultations.

5.7 Governance and Sustainability

The EOSC PID Policy establishes principles for community governance of PID Services and PSPs, responsive to the needs of research, open research and EOSC, oversight, justifiable costs and exit plans for PSPs. The Strategy recommends a governing group, national coordination and centralised support and long-term evaluation (to 2030). The EOSC PID Policy's governance principles could be applied to the proposed governance and national central support service in several important ways.

Recommendations:

- Operate with stakeholder input through advisory boards or steering committees representing Irish HEIs, research infrastructures, funding bodies and researchers.
- Actively gather feedback and adapt services (templates, guidance, support) based on actual user requirements.
- Implement clear performance monitoring mechanisms, track usage metrics and user satisfaction and provide regular reporting to funders and stakeholders.
- Maintain transparent budgeting, demonstrate cost-effectiveness compared to institutions working independently and ensure efficient use of funding.
- Develop contingency plans including documented processes, transferable resources, and clear handover procedures to ensure continuity if the service transitions or ends.

5.8 Legal and Ethical Considerations (GDPR and related obligations)

The EOSC PID Policy highlights the importance of ensuring that PID systems comply with GDPR, particularly where identifiers relate to individuals or include metadata that could be considered personal data. To support consistent and legally compliant practice, institutions will need clear, operational guidance on issues such as lawful processing, responding to erasure or correction requests and managing identifiers that reference sensitive or restricted content.

Recommendations:

The central support service should:

- Produce guidance and training covering lawful bases for processing, metadata minimisation, handling personal data in PID records and managing correction or erasure requests while maintaining PID resolvability.
- Monitor developments in EOSC and European data protection guidance and update national materials as needed, ensuring Ireland remains aligned with EU-level expectations around lawful processing and PIDs.

6. Conclusion and next steps

Ireland's PID Strategy demonstrates strong alignment with the EOSC PID Policy, sharing common commitments to interoperability, persistence, openness and sustainable governance. The national roadmap provides a clear foundation for coordinated adoption and infrastructure development across institutions. The gap analysis has identified key areas where focused enhancements and actionable next steps will strengthen Ireland's readiness for full participation in the EOSC ecosystem.

The next steps will centre on consolidating these findings into the existing National PID Strategy. This will involve translating the recommendations outlined in this report into clear, practical guidance that complements the recommendations and actions of the Strategy. Engagement with wider stakeholders via the [2025 National Open Research Festival](#) will ensure the recommendation is feasible, responsive to sector needs, and positioned for effective adoption within Ireland's open research landscape.

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